

The Public Utility Data Liberation Project: Providing Open Data For a Clean Energy Transition

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Abstract—A rapid and equitable energy transition needs a diversity of participants who are empowered to conduct research and intervene with high-quality accessible energy data. This paper describes the critical role of open data in creating a fair and equitable clean energy transition. To address this need, Catalyst Cooperative created the Public Utility Data Liberation (PUDL) project to bridge the gap between available and accessible U.S. energy data – publishing free and open-source energy data and collaborating with non-profits, scholars and local advocates working to decarbonize U.S. energy systems. This paper describes how PUDL processes and publishes data and its impact. Beyond PUDL’s functionality, this paper articulates the need for building an open-source ecosystem around PUDL and next steps for the long term sustainability of PUDL.

Index Terms—open source, open data, EIA, FERC, US energy system, data pipeline, outreach

I. INTRODUCTION

Rapid and equitable decarbonization to meet U.S. climate mitigation targets requires free, accessible, and open-source energy data. Federal agencies such as the Federal Energy Regulatory Commission (FERC), the Energy Information Administration (EIA), and the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) collect and publish primary U.S. energy system data. However, existing data formats and quality issues require extensive preprocessing, hindering research and advocacy efforts.

While existing commercial products such as S&P Global Market Intelligence [1] and the Hitachi Energy Velocity Suite [2] provide analysis-ready data, their opaque processing techniques and restrictions on re-use limit their usefulness in a research or advocacy context, and their high cost makes them generally inaccessible to small and/or under-resourced organizations working in the public interest [3].

Even when authors publish data and open-source code, they rarely commit resources to maintain or update repositories as new data becomes available; as a result, highly-skilled researchers replicate similar data preparation tasks with limited long-term value, while risking the introduction of downstream effects on model results [4]–[6].

Despite the acknowledged benefits of open-source models and data, energy research lags behind other multidisciplinary fields in “openness”, with open data availability as a key barrier [7]–[9]. Increased reliance on variable renewable energy sources, battery storage, and dispatchable demand are making energy system planning increasingly complex [9], [10]. Transitioning to a reliable, cost-effective, zero carbon energy system involves a growing number of stakeholders with divergent interests, technical capabilities, and economic resources at local to federal levels [11], [12].

A robust open-source ecosystem (OSE) would improve effective collaboration between academic researchers and policy analysts by reducing time spent on repetitive data cleaning and preparation tasks. Drawing on experience from multiple disciplines, external content contributors could integrate and maintain a larger number of datasets, to support a growing community of end-users. An OSE could sustain more frequent data releases, reducing user time spent on ad-hoc data integration between releases.

An OSE would improve the reproducibility of energy system research and facilitate comparisons between different modeling approaches, resulting in a more robust understanding of available decarbonization pathways. With well-defined criteria for inclusion of new analysis into the processing pipeline, broadly useful peer-reviewed analyses would be replicable, consistently updated with new data, and continuously deployed for others to build on. Researchers could use common industry data engineering frameworks and directly comparable data inputs, improving the reproducibility, scalability, and sustainability of their work [3], [13], [14].

In this context, an open-source, centralized energy data pipeline with a broad user base, well-supported and coordinated external contributors, and reliably updated outputs is needed to catalyze transformative and equitable energy investment, research, and policy developments. Anticipating this gap, Catalyst Cooperative has developed a robust open-source energy data processing pipeline called the Public Utility Data Liberation Project (PUDL) [15]. PUDL archives new data

from agency websites every month, regenerates and tests a wide variety of data products with automated nightly builds using the most recent version of the pipeline, and publishes versioned releases incorporating new data each quarter. Since 2016, the project has grown to support an expanding open energy research ecosystem.

In this pivotal decade for US climate action, an open-source ecosystem that expands the community of PUDL users and contributors could drive more impactful energy system research and extend the range of voices in key policy-making venues. Catalyst’s long-term vision is an open-source PUDL ecosystem that: 1) provides equitable access to high-quality energy data; 2) serves as a community repository of well-documented, reproducible data cleaning and analysis pipelines essential to energy system research and advocacy; 3) is accessible to users working with a variety of different tooling (e.g. Python, R, Microsoft Excel); and 4) is an inclusive and welcoming environment for users and contributors. Through continuous development and community engagement, PUDL strives to be a crucial building block for creating an equitable decarbonized future.

II. THE PUBLIC UTILITY DATA LIBERATION PROJECT

Catalyst’s PUDL project brings together operational and financial data that paints a detailed picture of the U.S. electricity system in a unified, continuously updated dataset. Among other formats, the data in PUDL is originally published as spreadsheets, CSV files, obsolete proprietary binary databases, XBRL documents, and large JSON files. Many of these data have formats that vary significantly from year to year and can change without notice. Catalyst harmonizes their structure across multiple decades of historical reporting, and uses both manual and machine learning techniques to link the datasets to each other so they can be used in tandem. The data describes entities ranging in scale from individual boilers, generators, and emissions control systems to whole power plants, electric utilities, and regional balancing authorities. The time resolution ranges from annual to hourly. As of mid-2024, PUDL incorporates data from roughly 20 different input sources, resulting in more than 200 published tables containing a total of more than 3,200 columns and approximately 20 GB of data. This data is distributed using file-based SQLite databases and Apache Parquet files.

The scope of the data available in PUDL has grown to include key datasets for energy modeling, utility financial analyses, and policy development. Current inputs include U.S. EIA Forms 860, 860M, 861, 923, and 930 as well as the EIA’s Annual Energy Outlook and bulk electricity data; FERC Forms 1 and 714; the EPA Continuous Emissions Monitoring System (CEMS), U.S. Census Bureau Demographic Profile 1, the National Renewable Energy Laboratory’s (NREL) Annual Technology Baseline (ATB), and the GridPath Resource Adequacy Toolkit. Catalyst is actively integrating financial data from the U.S. Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) Form 10-K, and connecting it to existing EIA and FERC data in PUDL [16].

The data from EIA Form 860 is the backbone of much of the PUDL database, as it provides the most extensive and well structured plant, utility, and generator level information. This includes data on electric utilities and non-utility generation at the plant and generator level. It also contains plant in-service and retirement dates, information about prime movers, generating capacity, energy sources, proposed generators, physical location, ownership, and FERC qualifying facility status. In recent years the EIA Form 860 has also begun providing detailed information about renewable energy and battery storage facilities.

Fewer electricity producers are required to report data to FERC than to EIA, but those who do, provide information via FERC Form 1 about their non-fuel operations and maintenance costs and capital investments on a plant-by-plant basis. This data is key for estimating the marginal cost of electricity (MCOE) generated by a facility, allowing for economic comparisons to other generation and demand side management options. FERC Form 1 also provides a detailed accounting of capital assets and liabilities. While this data is aggregated on a utility-wide basis, rather than at the plant level, it can still provide key insights into how a utility’s capital additions and retirements have affected its overall financial picture.

III. METHODOLOGY

PUDL has three core components: versioned archives of raw input data, a data processing pipeline, and a file-based data warehouse.

A. Raw Data Archives

Agencies frequently update published data without notice or explanation, and with no way to access past versions of the data. To ensure reproducible long-term access, PUDL archives monthly snapshots of its raw inputs on Zenodo [22]. Each version of each input is assigned a unique Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and can be accessed programmatically through Zenodo’s REST API. The value of these archives was highlighted in 2022 when FERC temporarily removed decades worth of energy system data from its website without notice [37].

B. Data Pipeline

The data pipeline follows an extract, transform, load (ETL) process: it ingests raw data from the archives, cleans and integrates it, and writes the resulting tables to SQLite and Apache Parquet files, while metadata is distributed as JSON using the Frictionless Data Package standard. Each release of the PUDL software contains a set of DOIs indicating which versions of the raw inputs it processed. This helps ensure that the outputs are reproducible.

The transform step of the ETL executes a number of standard data-cleaning operations, including:

- Harmonizing data types and formats across decades of historical reporting.
- Reconciling internally inconsistent reported attributes to identify canonical values. For instance, identifying the

most commonly reported latitude and longitude for a power plant.

- Imputing and backfilling missing data.
- Creating common identifiers for entities like plants and generators to allow linking datasets from different agencies.
- Standardizing categorical values that have been misspelled or whose definitions have changed over time.

In order to more easily integrate new data sources and address data quality concerns, PUDL utilizes Dagster, a data engineering orchestration framework, to address this complexity [17]. Dagster uses a declarative model to describe software defined assets, and the dependencies between them forming a directed acyclic graph (DAG). Each asset is typically a database table or a trained machine learning model. Once the DAG has been defined in Python, it can be executed and monitored using Dagster’s web-based user interface. Dagster can be deployed locally for development, or on scalable cloud computing resources in production. A portion of the PUDL data processing DAG is shown in Fig. 1.

C. File-based Data Warehouse

The PUDL ETL process generates a file-based data warehouse that can be used to support a wide variety of applications. Dagster assets are persisted to disk as both SQLite and Apache Parquet files for use locally in development, or automatic distribution following successful data validation in our nightly build and release processes (see below). File-based outputs were chosen to enable both local and remote analysis, easy distribution and archiving, and to avoid the need for users to authenticate with cloud services. The Parquet files may be easily loaded into Google BigQuery or another analytical database if desired.

D. Automated Nightly Builds

For continuous integration and deployment purposes the complete ETL, all software tests and data validations are run each night using a Google Batch job kicked off by a GitHub Action. This ensures that new code and updated data are constantly being tested. After a successful nightly build the outputs are copied to the Amazon Web Services (AWS) Open Data Registry [18], and our Datasette [23] instance is redeployed. A public PUDL dataset on Kaggle pulls fresh data from AWS weekly. These distribution methods make it easy for users to integrate PUDL data directly into other workflows, and ensures that the public always has access to the most recent data. Old nightly build outputs are overwritten whenever a new build is successful.

E. Machine Learning Workflows

Datasets from different sources often refer to the same physical entities but lack shared IDs that would allow the data to be easily used in tandem. Catalyst has integrated automated entity matching (record linkage) processes into the PUDL ETL to facilitate such usage. For example, PUDL connects financial data published by FERC to physical energy system

data reported to EIA. Both datasets refer to the same utilities, power plants, and generators, so a match between them can be modeled using shared attributes like plant and utility names, nameplate capacity, and primary fuel type, as shown in Fig. 2 [19]. This linkage provides a more complete picture of utility and power plant economics, in some cases demonstrating that replacing fossil power plants with renewable energy sources is both economically beneficial and technically feasible while maintaining grid reliability. These entity matching processes can mostly eliminate the tedious and sometimes intractable task of building a manual mapping. PUDL’s entity matching system uses the Splink library [20], which implements the Fellegi-Sunter algorithm, and relies on DuckDB for linking local datasets with up to tens of millions of records.

Catalyst is currently integrating a machine learning model into PUDL based on LayoutLM [21] to extract structured tabular data from unstructured regulatory filings available only as PDFs. For example, Exhibit 21 of the U.S. SEC Form 10K describes the parent-subsidary ownership relationships of U.S. corporations [16], but is not published in a structured document. This data is necessary to understand the political economy of utility companies and their complex web of shared financial interests.

F. Data Validation

PUDL has a growing collection of data validations that are run in the nightly builds to avoid publishing data with known issues. They validate the data against stated expectations, such as:

- The heat content of various fuel types is within expected bounds.
- Coal ash, moisture, mercury, sulfur, etc. content are within expected bounds.
- Generator heat rates and capacity factors are realistic for the type of prime mover being reported.
- The expected number of records within each table.
- No entirely N/A columns.

A variety of database integrity checks and column-specific constraints are also validated either during data processing or when the data is loaded into SQLite.

G. Versioned Data Releases

Catalyst periodically publishes versioned data releases based on the nightly build outputs to ensure long-term access to PUDL outputs. The data is archived on Zenodo and assigned a DOI [22]. Versioned releases are also published to the AWS Open Data Registry [18] and retained for multiple years. Like the nightly builds, each versioned release includes all available outputs and can be accessed by many different tools without the need to set up a bespoke software environment [24]. This system makes it easy to do frequent releases and iterate based on user feedback. Data releases are currently quarterly.

IV. PUDL IMPACT

PUDL data has been used by researchers, non-profits, US government analysts, and industry experts working on energy

Fig. 1. A small portion of the PUDL ETL pipeline showing dependencies between different asset groups.

Fig. 2. Splink provides interactive charts of the model weights that make it easier for downstream users to provide feedback without advanced understanding of the underlying model mechanics.

system modeling [25], energy policy and regulation [26], electricity planning [27], environmental and health impact assessments of the US energy system [28], utility economic and financial analyses [29], and energy market modeling [30]. For instance, PUDL data was used by Energy Innovation to reveal that 80% of existing coal plants were either slated to retire within five years, or more expensive to operate than new wind or solar generation. Accounting for health and environmental impacts of coal production, no existing coal plants in the United States were deemed ‘economic’ to continue operating [28]. In 2024, PUDL data was used to show that clean energy development is not driving electricity price increases and high energy burdens on U.S. households, and rather that rate increases can be attributed to wildfire related costs and natural gas price volatility [31].

PUDL’s data is at the foundation of an expanding research ecosystem: a growing number of energy system modeling and data projects rely on PUDL data to gain insight into

the U.S. electricity landscape. The PowerGenome project out of Princeton’s ZEROLab uses PUDL data to compile inputs for the GenX power system model [32], with efforts underway to expand support for other models. The Open Grid Emissions (OGE) Initiative at Singularity Energy grew out of a collaboration with UC Davis PhD student Greg Miller and his EPA EmPOWER Air Data Challenge project [33]. OGE uses PUDL data to provide hourly electricity emissions intensity by balancing authority. PUDL is also one of the primary datasets behind RMI’s Utility Transition Hub, which focuses on presenting useful utility financial data to regulators and climate policy advocates [34]. Catalyst is currently working with the maintainers of the PyPSA-USA model at Stanford to integrate PUDL as a primary input dataset [35], and integrating data necessary to run the GridPath model with support from GridLab [36].

PUDL is also improving research productivity and reproducibility. By reducing time spent on laborious and difficult to

replicate manual data preparation, PUDL enables researchers and policymakers to focus on applying their domain knowledge to novel problems. PUDL has empowered a diverse array of stakeholders by providing equitable access to high-quality energy data, reducing information asymmetry in regulatory proceedings, and supporting rigorous, reproducible research. As the energy landscape continues to evolve, PUDL will be a crucial resource for building a decarbonized and equitable energy future.

V. LOOKING FORWARD

A. *New Data*

Although PUDL has significantly improved the availability of analysis-ready open U.S. energy system data, there are still many valuable sources that are too hard for practitioners to access. Alongside ongoing maintenance and updates to the many datasets that have already been integrated, Catalyst foresees expanding PUDL's scope to include data about natural gas, electricity market transactions, transmission and distribution assets, and utility ownership. Millions of pages of regulatory filings currently accessible only as PDFs via state utility commission websites also need to be made more accessible to stakeholders who can't afford expensive document search and summary services.

FERC Form 2, the Pipeline and Hazardous Materials Safety Administration's Annual Natural Gas Report, and various EIA forms can provide insight into who owns existing natural gas infrastructure, where it is, and how much residual capital remains in the system. FERC's Electric Quarterly Reports [38] details billions of electricity market transactions over the last decade in both restructured and vertically integrated wholesale markets. Understanding the financial entanglements between different electric and gas utilities can expose anti-competitive behavior and help policymakers understand which electric utilities are encumbered by ties to fossil fuel producers or capital sunk into natural gas infrastructure. Liberating these data sources and integrating them into PUDL alongside existing electricity data will help address inequities and information asymmetries, drive real energy policy impact, and empower more people to take an active role in determining the country's energy future.

Cheap cloud computing and object storage combined with increasingly powerful open source document indexing systems and large language models (LLMs) may also enable the development of an ergonomic public search, summary, and retrieval interface for regulatory filings, leveling the playing field between large companies and small public-interest intervenors in a number of regulatory venues.

B. *Open-Source Energy Modeling Inputs*

Catalyst anticipates developing and maintaining comprehensive open data inputs for open source energy system models as a high priority in the coming years. Open source energy system models, such as GenX, PyPSA-USA and GridPath are used by researchers and public-interest policy analysts to explore long-term power system planning options. Catalyst is working

to integrate new data inputs widely used in energy modeling, such as the National Renewable Energy Laboratory's Annual Technology Baseline, hourly demand and generation from EIA Form 930, and projections of future fuel prices, energy supply and consumption, and carbon dioxide emissions by sector and region from the EIA Annual Energy Outlook.

C. *Community Development*

With funding from the National Science Foundation's Pathways to Enable Open-Source Ecosystems (NSF POSE) over the next 12 months Catalyst will be assessing the viability of an open-source ecosystem model for ongoing development of open energy system data, identifying key user needs, addressing barriers faced by contributors, and socializing PUDL more widely. Key project activities include the development of a contributor onboarding process, an annual user survey, and improvements to CI/CD infrastructure. Funding will also support the development of community governance to better support the project long-term.

D. *Training Support for the Next Generation*

Academic researchers play an important role in helping policymakers and other stakeholders understand the energy transition [11]. However, it is not uncommon for energy scholars to lack the technical skills necessary to wield the more complex models and larger datasets required to explore scenarios dominated by renewable energy.

Early career researchers are often responsible for identifying and preparing data for analysis, but may have little formal training in software engineering and data management. In many research fields, especially in the social sciences, foundational data and software engineering skills are learned informally and without attention to modern best practices [13]. The rapid evolution of data and computational tools can also result in generational divides, making it difficult for graduate students to learn these technical skills from their advisors.

As PUDL's data catalog grows and the open-source energy data landscape matures, students stand to benefit tremendously from using open data in their research. However, many need an accessible onramp to move from beginner to intermediate proficiency in software engineering and data management. With support from the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation and in collaboration with The Carpentries, over the next 18 months Catalyst will be developing and delivering an open source energy data curriculum, hosting a virtual seminar series, and convening a student-centered open energy data workshop. By offering training grounded in the practical experience of cleaning and distributing energy data through PUDL, Catalyst hopes to expand participation in existing communities of practice, foster openness in energy research, and equip a new generation of students with the tools necessary to productively participate in the energy transition.

VI. CONCLUSION

Energy research lags behind neighboring fields in the openness of data, underscoring the urgent need for more accessible

and open energy data. The Public Utility Data Liberation project addresses this gap by providing impactful open-source data essential for research and policy-making. As PUDL continues to grow, Catalyst’s aim is to expand its reach and ensure the long-term sustainability of an open-source ecosystem.

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